

The Fellowship of Goodness 同善社 (Tongshanshe)

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Tongshanshe, the Fellowship of Goodness, was one of the largest redemptive societies in China before 1949. It was also labeled as a counterrevolutionary *huidaomen* (会道门) group by the Chinese Communist Party. In Chinese, the term “*huidaomen*” is composed of three different words: *hui*, *dao*, and *men*. “*Hui*”, “*Dao*”, and “*Men*” refer to any organization, association, or society composed of people who share similar interests or religious ideas. It can be either religious or secular or even both. Essentially, *huidaomen* was never a unified, monolithic organization in Chinese society. It was more like a general category and a generic term the government used to describe all voluntary associations. The term “*huidaomen*” has its precedent in late imperial China under the name “White Lotus Teachings.” The White Lotus sect was originally a lay Buddhist movement initiated by Monk Huiyuan of Lushan in the early fifth century. According to B.J. Ter Haar, the name “White Lotus” was used by non-elites as an autonym for lay Buddhist gatherings before the mid-fourteenth century. From the sixteenth century on, “White Lotus” was more and more frequently used and finally became a label for all potentially rebellious groups related to religion. Ter Haar further points out that by the late Ming dynasty, Christianity, millenarian teachings, lay Buddhist, and even sexual techniques were all labeled “White Lotus.” But people within such groups did not necessarily call themselves “White Lotus.” This label existed only in official propaganda. “White Lotus” was only a generic term without precise specifications. The government could use it as a political label for all the voluntary associations that had rebellious potentials. The PRC’s use of “*huidaomen*” came from the same logic of political labeling. In 2004, the Chinese Academy of Social Science published two-volume primary sources on *huidaomen* called *A Collection of Historical Materials on the Chinese Huidaomen: Their Organization and Distribution across A Century*. The sources of this collection mainly come from more than 3,500 local gazetteers published in the PRC after October of 1949. In this collection of sources, the compilation committee defines *huidaomen* clearly as “feudal associations that operated secretly in order to spread their religious teachings.” The book points out that the term “*huidaomen*” began to be used since the early PRC when the new government noticed the widespread networks of secret societies in China. Based on the information provided by the more than three thousand local gazetteers in *A Collection of Historical Materials on the Chinese Huidaomen* and my own case study of Poyang County in Jiangxi, I accept a broader definition of *huidaomen*, as the Chinese Academy of Social Science does. Almost all voluntary groups in China were indeed labeled as *huidaomen* from the late 1940s onward in political campaigns. It is inappropriate to define *huidaomen* exclusively as religious societies. Tongshanshe was one of the largest nation-wide redemptive societies in China during the Republican Era. During the late Qing period, Peng Ruzun (1868-1950) of Yongchuan County in Sichuan Province (now Chongqing) who was a former follower of the Way of Anterior Heaven (Xiantiandao) established Tongshanshe. Peng advocated a secular way of religious practice that participants in the Tongshanshe could become immortals through self-cultivation without fasting or becoming monks. Such secularized and simplified religious practice was widely welcomed. In 1910, Peng left Sichuan and went to Beijing to preach. Peng’s trip to Beijing gained tremendous support from former aristocrats of the Qing Dynasty and the leading warlords, including Duan Qirui and Cao Kun. In 1917, during the warlord period, Tongshanshe officially registered at the Northern Warlords Government in Beijing. Tongshanshe also established its central headquarters in Beijing. The government then provided Tongshanshe with formal support in developing branches across China. By

1923, Tongshanshe had already established provincial-level organizations in all provinces in China. In Beijing, Tongshanshe ran a publishing house that published a number of religious books on self-cultivation and morality. Tongshanshe also functioned as a charity organization providing support for funerals of ordinary people and mass education. In 1925, Peng built another Tongshanshe headquarters in Wuhan and claimed that Tongshanshe had a membership of over one million people. The name "Tongshanshe" even became a "free-floating signifier" of similar self-cultivation groups which shows the exceptional popularity of Tongshanshe in China. According to my study, Tongshanshe was largely an elite-based religious organization. Tongshanshe members were primarily rich merchants and even local politicians. Such an elite base was in sharp contrast to many traditional sectarian groups in China which were more attractive to the marginalized groups. Tongshanshe embraced religious syncretism, similar to many new religious organizations since the late Qing. It had widely absorbed Buddhism, Daoism, and Chinese popular religion. But Tongshanshe was predominantly a salvationist group. According to Tongshanshe's teachings, humans were living in a morally degenerating society. Peng Ruzun claimed that the end of the world was coming -- only those who firmly believed in Tongshanshe's teachings would survive the final apocalypse. The interpretation of Tongshanshe's millenarianism was not unified. Tongshanshe in different regions responded to the "end of the world" in diverse ways. Many local Tongshanshe groups in Southern China absorbed local military forces and practiced traditional Chinese martial arts, believing that martial arts would protect people from the final apocalypse. Other people, possibly under Peng Ruzun's instruction, believed that a new emperor would be born in China and would defeat all secular political powers. Both the Nationalist Government before 1949 and the Communist regime after 1949 saw Tongshanshe as a leading counterrevolutionary religious organization. From 1927 to the end of the Nationalist regime in 1949 on mainland China, the Nationalist government banned Tongshanshe multiple times. Due to the Nationalist Government's weak control of rural society, however, such suppressive policies were not carried out effectively outside big cities. After 1949, the Communist Party launched waves of Anti-Counterrevolutionary Campaigns. Labeled as a leading huidaomen group, Tongshanshe organizations were fatally destroyed by such campaigns and basically disappeared on the mainland. Tongshanshe also established its organizations in Taiwan and many Chinese communities in Southeast Asia. It continues operating today.

Date Range: 1910 CE - 1951 CE

Region: Poyang Lake Area

Region tags: Asia, East Asia, China, Poyang County, Poyang Lake, Jiangxi Province

Poyang Lake is the largest fresh-water lake in China. It was a major transportation center and grain production center in Southern China

Status of Participants:

- ✓ Elite
- ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Sources

Print sources for understanding this subject:

- Source 1: Zhongguo huidaomen shiliao jicheng bianzuan weiyuanhui, ed., Zhongguo huidaomen shiliao jicheng: jin bainian lai huidaomen de zuzhi yu fenbu [A collection of Historical Materials on the Chinese Huidaomen: Their Organization and Distribution Across A Century], 2 vols. Beijing: Zhongguo shehui kexue chubanshe, 2004.
- Source 2: Li, Shiyu. Xiandai huabei mimi zongjiao [Contemporary Secret Religions in Northern China]. Shanghai: Shanghai wenyi chubanshe, 1990.

- Source 3: Nedostup, Rebecca. *Superstitious Regimes: Religion and the Politics of Chinese Modernity*. Cambridge: Harvard University Press, 2009.
- Source 1: Lo, Shih-chieh, “Kangzhan wanqi de minbian yu defang shehui - yi Pingyang de daodaohui yu tongshanshe wei taolun zhongxin [The Daodaohui and Tongshanshe: A Case Study of Popular Uprising and Local Society in the Latter Part of the Second Sino-Japanese War],” *Chinese Studies*, Issue 36, Vol. 2, June 2018.
- Source 2: Goossaert, Vincent and David Palmer. *The Religious Question in Modern China*. Chicago: The University of Chicago Press, 2011.

Online sources for understanding this subject:

- Source 1 URL: <https://baike.baidu.com/item/%E5%90%8C%E5%96%84%E7%A4%BE/54623871>
- Source 1 Description: A very brief introduction from Baidu Encyclopedia 百度百科.

General Variables

Membership/Group Interactions

Are other religious groups in cultural contact with target religion:

– Yes

Notes: To many rural participants of Tongshanshe, especially in the cases of female participants, they saw Tongshanshe simply as a Buddhist group. Because Tongshanshe adopted religious syncretism, they welcomed all religious traditions in their rituals. Many people could not clearly distinguish Tongshanshe from other religious groups. Tongshanshe groups in the urban areas might have a stronger elite base.

↳ Is the cultural contact competitive:

– No

↳ Is the cultural contact accommodating/pluralistic:

– Yes

↳ Is the cultural contact neutral:

– Yes

↳ Is there violent conflict (within sample region):

– No

Notes: I don't see violent competition between Tongshanshe and other religious groups, but violent conflicts against the secular regimes occurred multiple times during both the Republican era and the early PRC.

↳ Is there violent conflict (with groups outside the sample region):

– No

Does the religious group have a general process/system for assigning religious affiliation:

– No

Does the religious group actively proselytize and recruit new members:

– Yes

Notes: Unlike some other large redemptive societies such as the Yiguandao, Tongshanshe had a much stronger elite base in expanding its membership and religious networks. In the case of Poyang, Tongshanshe members were mostly well-educated rich merchant class, some were even political figures at the local level and members of the Nationalist Party (although the Nationalist Government banned Tongshanshe). According to limited statistical data in Poyang, Tongshanshe members were mostly male, merchants, and educated. Among the 283 former Tongshanshe members in the sample, 247 were male, accounting for 87% of the total membership. Only 36 were female. 174 of the 283 TSS members were merchants, which was 61% of the total membership. 10% of the former members were housewives (all female), 9% were artisans, 5% doctors, 3% students, 2% the urban poor, 2% military or civil officials, 2% landlords. Only the seven landlords and two fishermen can be categorized into the agricultural population (many landlords actually resided in the Poyang County Seat without doing any agricultural work). Among the 36 female members, 29 were housewives, accounting for 81% of the female membership. Taiwanese scholar Shih-Chieh Lo's case study of Wenzhou also indicates that over half of the TSS members came from the upper-class, such as intellectuals and civil and military officials. Interestingly, the Poyang Merchant Association, established in the late Qing, was almost an overlapping association with the Tongshanshe. Tongshanshe was a major socializing channel where big merchants in Poyang came to know each other and build commercial cooperations. High-level leaders within the Merchant Association in Poyang were often Tongshanshe leaders too. Tongshanshe members from non-elite classes could rarely participate in leadership roles of Tongshanshe.

↳ Is proselytizing mandated for religious professionals:

– Yes

↳ Is proselytizing mandated for all adherents:

– No

Notes: Although proselytizing was not mandated for ordinary members of Tongshanshe, new members were required to pay a membership fee upon joining Tongshanshe. It offered incentives for Tongshanshe members to recruit new people.

↳ Is missionary work mandated for religious professionals:

– No

Notes: There were no strict religious professionals in Tongshanshe. Even leaders of Tongshanshe at the local level had other jobs too. Missionary work was highly encouraged for local leaders, although not mandatory.

↳ Is missionary work mandated for all adherents:

– No

↳ Is proselytization coercive:

– No

Does the religion have official political support

– Yes

Notes: In 1910, Peng Ruzun, the founder of Tongshanshe, left Sichuan and went to Beijing to preach. Peng's trip to Beijing gained tremendous support from former aristocrats of the Qing Dynasty and the leading warlords, including Duan Qirui and Cao Kun. In 1917, during the warlord period, Tongshanshe officially registered at the Northern Warlords Government in Beijing. Tongshanshe also established its central headquarters in Beijing. The government then provided Tongshanshe with formal support in developing branches across China. By 1923, Tongshanshe had already established provincial-level organizations in all provinces in China. In 1925, Peng built another Tongshanshe headquarters in Wuhan and claimed that Tongshanshe had a membership of over one million people. In 1927, however, due to the dramatic changes in Chinese politics, the religious freedom that TSS had gained was rejected by the new Nationalist Government. A 1927 meeting concluded that the Nationalist Government would continue granting religious freedom to the Chinese people if only the premise that Tongshanshe must be eliminated could be fulfilled. But Tongshanshe continued operating after the 1927 ban. Some Tongshanshe groups changed their names, some went underground. In many rural areas, however, Tongshanshe's activities went on without any intervention from the local government. Participants in the Tongshanshe were even not aware of the Nationalist Government's ban. The Nationalist Government banned Tongshanshe multiple times again throughout the 1940s, but the government was not effective enough to control of growth of Tongshanshe. After the regime change in 1949, Tongshanshe was labeled as a counterrevolutionary huidaomen group and banned by the new socialist regime. The PRC launched severe crackdowns against Tongshanshe throughout China. Most Tongshanshe groups were destroyed in the early 1950s.

Reference: Rebecca Nedostup. *Superstitious Regimes*. Harvard Univ Council on East Asian. isbn: 9780674035997.

↳ Are the priests paid by polity:

– No

↳ Is religious infrastructure paid for by the polity:

– No

↳ Are the head of the polity and the head of the religion the same figure:

– No

↳ Are political officials equivalent to religious officials:

– No

↳ Is religious observance enforced by the polity:

– No

↳ Polity legal code is roughly coterminous with religious code:

– No

↳ Polity provides preferential economic treatment (e.g. tax, exemption)

– No

Is there a conception of apostasy in the religious group:

– No

Size and Structure

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (estimated population, numerical):

– Field doesn't know

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (% of sample region population, numerical):

– Field doesn't know

Nature of religious group [please select one]:

– Large religious group (with smaller religious groups not officially allowed but in practice tolerated)

Are there recognized leaders in the religious group:

– Yes

↳ Is there a hierarchy among these leaders:

– Yes

↳ A single leader of a local community:

– No

↳ Multiple religious communities each with its own leader, no hierarchy among these leaders:

– Yes

Notes: At the county level and below, Tongshanshe's structure was relatively chaotic and not fully institutionalized. There were many Tongshanshe groups at the same level without a clear hierarchical structure.

↳ "Regional" leaders who oversee one or more local leader(s) (e.g. bishops):
– No

↳ A single leader for the religious group that oversees all other leaders in the sample region:
– No

↳ A council or group of leaders for the religious group that oversees all other leaders in the sample region:
– No

↳ Estimate how many levels there are in the hierarchy of religious leadership:
– Number of levels [numeric value]: 16

Notes: Tongshanshe had a clear organizational structure. In the administrative sphere, Tongshanshe followed a hierarchical order from the national level to the sub-county level. At the national level, Tongshanshe had one central headquarters (zonghao) and a central office of administration (zong shiwusuo). The central headquarters was originally established by Peng Ruzun in Beijing. Peng then relocated the central headquarters to his hometown in Sichuan Province. The central office of administration refers to the new headquarters built in Wuhan in 1925, assisting the old headquarters with administrative affairs in each province. Peng Ruzun was the single highest leader in the Tongshanshe known as the "venerable master (shizun)." At the provincial level, there was a provincial headquarters in each province. Peng Ruzun directly appointed leaders of each provincial headquarters. Under the provincial level, the Tongshanshe network was further divided into county branches. The heads of the county branches were called the master of goodness (shanzhang) and the vice-master of goodness (fu shanzhang). Both the masters and vice-masters were elected from the local Tongshanshe leaders. Below the county level were local offices of administrative affairs (shiwusuo). In the religious sphere, Tongshanshe was even more meticulously divided into sixteen hierarchical levels. Level one to level three referred to lay believers in the Tongshanshe without any administrative or religious authority. People from level four above were given the authority to preach and introduce new people into Tongshanshe. Level five to level seven were appointed by people above level ten. All the people above level eight were appointed by Peng Ruzun himself. People above level nine were considered high-level religious leaders in the Tongshanshe, and their number was very small. Level sixteen was the highest in Tongshanshe. Only Peng Ruzun himself belonged to this class.

↳ Are leaders believed to possess supernatural powers or qualities:
– Yes

Notes: Only Peng Ruzun, the highest leader of Tongshanshe, was believed to possess

supernatural powers. Instead of religious leaders in many former White Lotus groups who claimed themselves to be the incarnation of certain deities, people's belief in Peng didn't have much religious justification, and Peng was not understood as god (although he certainly had supernatural qualities). Peng's role was not emphasized in people's daily religious practice. It was only during the regime change period that many people believed that Peng and his son would be the future emperor(s) of China so that peace and prosperity would be rebuilt on earth.

↳ Powers are acquired by individual deeds carried out in past lives:
– No

↳ Powers are acquired by individual deeds carried out in the current life:
– No

↳ Powers are inherited:
– Yes

↳ Powers are culturally transmitted from a supernatural being:
– No

↳ Powers are culturally transmitted from another human (e.g. teacher):
– No

↳ Powers are associated with leadership office they assume:
– Yes

↳ Are religious leaders chosen:
– Yes

↳ A leader chooses his/her own replacement:
– No

↳ A leader's retinue or ministers chooses the new leader:
– No

↳ Other leaders in the religious group choose that leader:
– Yes

↳ A political leader chooses the leader:

– No

↳ Other members of the leader's congregation choose the leader:

– Yes

↳ All members of the religious group in the sample region participate in choosing the leader:

– No

↳ Communication with supernatural power(s) believed to be part of the selection process:

– Yes

Notes: Spiritual writing or communication with the spiritual medium was always part of Tongshanshe's ceremonies. From a secular perspective, however, these practices can be easily manipulated or interpreted at random.

↳ Are leaders considered fallible:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Are close followers or disciples of a religious leader required to obediently and unquestionably accept the leader's pronouncements on all matters:

– Yes

Scripture

Does the religious group have scriptures:

Scripture is a generic term used to designate revered texts that are considered particularly authoritative and sacred relative to other texts. Strictly speaking, it refers to written texts, but there are also "oral scriptures" (e.g. the Vedas of India).

– Yes

Notes: Since my research site doesn't provide any written records of Tongshanshe's scriptures, the following information is directly quoted from Wang Chien-chuan, trans David Ownby., "The Composition and Distribution of the Tongshanshe, with a Focus on the Ten Thousand Buddha Scripture (1917-1949)," in Kenneth Dean, Richard Madsen, David Palmer, edited., *Text and Context in the Modern History of Chinese Religions*. Leiden: Brill, 2020. p57. Tongshanshe scriptures basically include: "1. Texts written by the group leader, such as Records of Sayings of Master [Peng] Huilong who Saves the World (Huilong shizun pudu yulu 迴龍師尊普度語錄) and Tales of the Ancient Man who Identified and Destroyed Fifty Great Demons (Shugu laoren zhipo wushi damoguan 述古老人指破五十大魔關). 2. Accounts composed by believers, such as Accounts of Hearing the Dharma (Wenfa shuji 聞法述記), Records of Returning Home (Huixiang yulu 回鄉語錄), or Directions for Returning Home (Huanxiang zhizhi 還鄉直指). 3. Spirit-writing texts and morality books linked to the Tongshanshe, such as Precious

Notes from the Depths of Obscurity, Record of the Banquet of the Peach of Immortality (Pantao yanji 蟠桃宴記), and The Great Way of the Five Cardinal Relationships (Wulun dadao 五倫大道). 4. Tongshanshe documents and regulations, such as: Regulations of the Tongshanshe (Tongshanshe zhangcheng 同善社章程), Collected Temple Rules (Fotang guize hebian 佛堂規則合編), Promulgation of the Patriarch's Lineage (Zupai jiexiao 祖派揭曉), Collection of Notifications of the Tongshanshe Headquarters (Tongshan zongshe chuandan huibian 同善總社傳單彙編). 5. Morality books in wide circulation, such as the [Yuan] Liaofan's Lessons for His Son (Liaofan xunzishu 了凡訓子書). 6. Daoist neidan cultivation texts, such as The True Teaching for Chanting the Way (Changdao zhenyan 唱道真言), Proof of the Golden Immortal (Jinxian lunzheng 金仙論證), and Scripture of the Life of Wisdom (Huimingjing 慧命經). 7. Scriptures unique to the Tongshanshe, such as The Scripture of the Completion of the Way (Liaodaojing 了道經)."

Reference: Philip Clart, David Ownby, Chien-chuan Wang. Text and Context in the Modern History of Chinese Religions. Religion in Chinese Societies. isbn: 9789004424135.

↳ Are they written:
– Yes

↳ Are they oral:
– Yes

↳ Is there a story (or a set of stories) associated with the origin of scripture:
– I don't know

↳ Are the scriptures alterable:
– Field doesn't know

↳ Are there formal institutions (i.e. institutions that are authorized by the religious community or political leaders) for interpreting the scriptures:
– No

↳ Is there a select group of people trained in transmitting the scriptures:
– No

↳ Is there a codified canon of scriptures:
– No

Architecture, Geography

Is monumental religious architecture present:
– No

Are there different types of religious monumental architecture:

– No

Is iconography present:

– No

Are there specific sites dedicated to sacred practice or considered sacred:

– No

Are pilgrimages present:

– No

Beliefs

Burial and Afterlife

Is a spirit-body distinction present:

Answer “no” only if personhood (or consciousness) is extinguished with death of the physical body. Answering yes does not necessarily imply the existence of Cartesian mind/body dualism, merely that some element of personhood (or consciousness) survives the death of the body.

– No

Belief in afterlife:

– No

Reincarnation in this world:

– No

Are there special treatments for adherents' corpses:

– No

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

– No

Are grave goods present:

– No

Are formal burials present:

– No

Supernatural Beings

Are supernatural beings present:

– Yes

↳ A supreme high god is present:

– No

Notes: Tongshanshe members worshipped a wide range of gods in Daoism, Buddhism, and Chinese popular religion instead of a supreme high god.

↳ Previously human spirits are present:

– No

↳ Non-human supernatural beings are present:

– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings can be seen:

– No

↳ These supernatural beings can be physically felt:

– No

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge of this world:

– Yes

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge restricted to particular domain of human affairs:

– No

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region:

– No

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge unrestricted within the sample region:

– Yes

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge unrestricted outside of sample region:

– Yes

↳ Non-human supernatural beings can see you everywhere normally visible (in public):

– Yes

↳ Non-human supernatural beings can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home):

– Yes

↳ Non-human supernatural beings can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives):

– Yes

↳ Non-human supernatural beings knows your basic character (personal essence):

– Yes

↳ Non-human supernatural beings know what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight):

– Field doesn't know

Notes: The gods in Tongshanshe know that the end of the world will come and many people will die as a consequence of the final apocalypse, but it's unclear whether they know what each person will do or not.

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have other knowledge of this world:

– Yes [specify]: They know how the world started and how the world will end.

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have deliberate causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings can reward:

– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings can punish:

– Yes

- ↳ These supernatural beings have indirect causal efficacy in the world:
 - No
- ↳ These supernatural beings exhibit positive emotion:
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ These supernatural beings exhibit negative emotion:
 - Yes
- ↳ These supernatural beings possess hunger:
 - No
- ↳ These supernatural beings possess/exhibit some other feature:
 - No
- ↳ Mixed human-divine beings are present:
 - No
- ↳ Does the religious group possess a variety of supernatural beings:
 - Yes
- ↳ Organized by kinship based on a family model:
 - No
- ↳ Organized hierarchically:
 - No
- ↳ Power of beings is domain specific:
 - No
- ↳ Other organization for pantheon:
 - No

Supernatural Monitoring

Is supernatural monitoring present:

This refers to surveillance by supernatural beings of humans' behaviour and/or thought particularly as it relates to social norms or potential norm violations.

– Yes

- ↳ There is supernatural monitoring of prosocial norm adherence in particular:
Prosocial norms are norms that enhance cooperation among members of the group, including obviously “moral” or “ethical” norms, but also extending to norms concerning honouring contracts and oaths, providing hospitality, coming to mutual aid in emergencies, etc.

– Yes

- ↳ Supernatural beings care about taboos:

– Field doesn't know

- ↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of coreligionists:

– Field doesn't know

- ↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of members of other religions:

– Field doesn't know

- ↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of members of other polities:

– Field doesn't know

- ↳ Supernatural beings care about sex:

– Field doesn't know

- ↳ Supernatural beings care about lying:

– Yes

- ↳ Supernatural beings care about honouring oaths:

– Field doesn't know

- ↳ Supernatural beings care about laziness:

– Field doesn't know

- ↳ Supernatural beings care about sorcery:

– Field doesn't know

- ↳ Supernatural beings care about non-lethal fighting:
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about shirking risk:
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about disrespecting elders:
 - Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about gossiping:
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about property crimes:
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about proper ritual observance:
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about performance of rituals:
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about conversion of non-religionists:
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about economic fairness:
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about personal hygiene:
 - No
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about other:
 - I don't know

Do supernatural beings mete out punishment:

– Yes

↳ Is the cause or agent of supernatural punishment known:

– Yes

↳ Done only by high god:

– No

↳ Done by many supernatural beings:

– Yes

↳ Done through impersonal cause-effect principle:

– Yes

Notes: Good deeds and devotion to Tongshanshe will be rewarded, whereas moral degeneration will be punished at the end of the world.

↳ Done by other entities or through other means [specify]

– No

↳ Is the reason for supernatural punishment known:

– Yes

↳ Done to enforce religious ritual-devotional adherence:

– Yes

↳ Done to enforce group norms:

– Yes

↳ Done to inhibit selfishness:

– Yes

↳ Done randomly:

– No

↳ Other [specify]

– No

↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in the afterlife:

– No

↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in this lifetime:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural punishments in this life are highly emphasized by the religious group:

– Yes

↳ Punishment in this life consists of bad luck:

– No

↳ Punishment in this life consists of political failure:

– No

↳ Punishment in this life consists of defeat in battle:

– No

↳ Punishment in this life consists of crop failure or bad weather:

– Yes

↳ Punishment in this life consists of disaster on journeys.

– Yes

↳ Punishment in this life consists of mild sensory displeasure:

– No

↳ Punishment in this life consists of extreme sensory displeasure:

– No

↳ Punishment in this life consists of sickness or illness:

– Yes

↳ Punishment in this life consists of impaired reproduction:

– No

↳ Punishment in this life consists of bad luck visited on descendants:

– No

↳ Other [specify]

– Yes

Notes: Tongshanshe's teachings had a strong emphasis on human's moral degeneration and the end of the world as a consequence. Human, if not corrected their moral misbehavior, will suffer a wide range of natural disasters, warfare, and physical torture. Only other who behave morally and accept the teachings of the Tongshanshe will be saved.

Do supernatural beings bestow rewards:

– Yes

↳ Is the cause/purpose of supernatural rewards known:

– Yes

↳ Done only by high god:

– No

↳ Done by many supernatural beings:

– Yes

↳ Done through impersonal cause-effect principle:

– No

↳ Done to enforce religious ritual-devotional adherence:

– Yes

↳ Done to enforce group norms:

– Yes

↳ Done to inhibit selfishness:

– Yes

↳ Done randomly:

– No

↳ Supernatural rewards are bestowed out in the afterlife:

– No

↳ Supernatural rewards are bestowed out in this lifetime:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural rewards in this life are highly emphasized by the religious group:

– Yes

↳ Reward in this life consists of good luck:

– Yes

↳ Reward in this life consists of political success or power:

– No

↳ Reward in this life consists of success in battle:

– No

↳ Reward in this life consists of peace or social stability:

– Yes

↳ Reward in this life consists of healthy crops or good weather:

– Yes

↳ Reward in this life consists of success on journeys:

– Yes

↳ Reward in this life consists of mild sensory pleasure:

– No

↳ Reward in this life consists of extreme sensory pleasure:

– No

↳ Reward in this life consists of enhanced health:

– Yes

↳ Reward in this life consists of enhanced reproductive success:

– Yes

↳ Reward in this life consists of fortune visited on descendants:

– Yes

↳ Other [specify]

– No

Messianism/Eschatology

Are messianic beliefs present:

– Yes

Notes: In the case of Tongshanshe in Poyang and many other rural areas in Southern China, the belief in the end of the world was closely related to Tongshanshe's militarization. Many local Tongshanshe leaders encouraged people to practice martial arts or join the martial branches of Tongshanshe, in order to protect themselves and their families from the final calamities. The end of the world was interpreted as an overwhelming natural disaster and human warfare. The consequence was severe physical suffering of human beings. Only those who firmly believe in the Tongshanshe will be saved by the gods and enjoy everlasting peaceful life when the end of over.

↳ Is the messiah's whereabouts or time of coming known?

– No

↳ Is the messiah's purpose known:

– Yes

Notes: To save the world from moral degeneration and defeat the evil secular regime, and save those who practice Tongshanshe teachings faithfully.

↳ Messiah is a political figure who restores political rule:

– Yes

↳ Messiah is a priestly figure who restores religious traditions:

– Yes

↳ Other purpose:

– Yes [specify]: Salvation

Is an eschatology present:

– Yes

↳ Eschaton in this lifetime:

– Yes

Notes: Tongshanshe members believe that the end of the world will happen in this life time, although the dates are unknown. Faithful believers will be redeemed by gods and become immortals, whereas the unfaithful will perish.

↳ Eschaton at specified time in future:

– No

↳ Eschaton at unspecified time in near future:

– Yes

Notes: Tongshanshe members believed that the end of the world was very close to their time, although unspecified. During the regime change period from 1949 to the early 1950s, many people strongly believed that the end of the world was about to take place very soon. Some Tongshanshe groups even rebelled against the new Communist regime and interpreted the new regime as the beginning of the final apocalypse.

↳ Eschaton at unspecified time in distant future:

– No

↳ Eschaton at some other time:

– No

↳ Adherents need to perform specific tasks to bring about World's end:

– No

↳ Divine judgment event:

– No

Notes: There would not be a unified judgement day as we see in the case of Christian eschatology. However, humans will be judged based on the deeds and faithfulness.

↳ Restoration of the world:

– Yes

Notes: The world order will be restored after the end of time. Tongshanshe doesn't have a clear and unified eschatological system. Some say the faithful believers will become immortals and enjoy happiness forever. Some other Tongshanshe teachings focus more on the end of all secular political regimes and the restoration of a new Chinese dynasty under the rule of the highest Tongshanshe leader.

↳ Start of a new temporal cycle:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Establishment of a new political system:

– Yes

↳ Establishment of a new religious system:

– No

↳ Will anyone survive the eschaton:

– Yes

Notes: Only faithful Tongshanshe participants will survive.

↳ All religious in-group members will survive the eschaton:

– No

Notes: Only faithful followers in Tongshanshe will survive. Maintaining a membership only is not sufficient for survival.

↳ A subset of religion in-group members will survive the eschaton:

– Yes

↳ All members of the sample region will survive the eschaton:

– No

↳ Everyone in the world will survive the eschaton:

– No

↳ Other survival condition:

– No

Norms and Moral Realism

Are general social norms prescribed by the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: Moral values promoted by Tongshanshe were primarily traditional Confucian values. The five cardinal relationships and the right virtues of Confucianism remained the central moral cores of Tongshanshe's teachings. As a syncretic religious organization, the Inner Alchemy teachings of Daoism were also important parts of Tongshanshe. From this perspective, Tongshanshe's moral teachings were not significantly different from other Chinese religious traditions.

Is there a conventional vs. moral distinction in the religious group:

– No

Are there centrally important virtues advocated by the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: Aside from the beliefs in Confucian and Daoist moral values, the belief in the apocalypse played an important role in terms of reminding people that they must follow these moral teachings faithfully to avoid death during the end of time.

↳ Honesty / trustworthiness / integrity:

– Yes

↳ Courage (in battle):

– Field doesn't know

↳ Courage (generic):

– Yes

↳ Compassion / empathy / kindness / benevolence:

– Yes

↳ Mercy / forgiveness / tolerance:

– Yes

↳ Generosity / charity:

– Yes

↳ Selflessness / selfless giving:

– Yes

↳ Righteousness / moral rectitude:

– Yes

↳ Ritual purity / ritual adherence / abstention from sources of impurity:

– Yes

↳ Respectfulness / courtesy:

– Yes

↳ Familial obedience / filial piety:

– Yes

Notes: Tongshanshe basically adopted most of the traditional Confucian values in China. Filial piety remained one of the most important aspects of its moral teachings. Especially in the cases of women, women were still encouraged to obey their husbands, parents, and sons.

↳ Fidelity / loyalty:

– Yes

↳ Cooperation:

– Yes

↳ Independence / creativity / freedom:

– No

↳ Moderation / frugality:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Forbearance / fortitude / patience:

– Yes

↳ Diligence / self-discipline / excellence:

– Yes

↳ Assertiveness / decisiveness / confidence / initiative:

– No

↳ Strength (physical):

– No

↳ Power / status / nobility:

– No

↳ Humility / modesty:

– Yes

↳ Contentment / serenity / equanimity:

– Yes

↳ Joyfulness / enthusiasm / cheerfulness:
– Field doesn't know

↳ Optimism / hope:
– Yes

↳ Gratitude / thankfulness:
– Yes

↳ Reverence / awe / wonder:
– Yes

↳ Faith / belief / trust / devotion:
– Yes

↳ Wisdom / understanding:
– No

↳ Discernment / intelligence:
– No

↳ Beauty / attractiveness:
– No

↳ Cleanliness (physical) / orderliness:
– Field doesn't know

↳ Other important virtues advocated by the religious group:
– No

Practices

Membership Costs and Practices

Does membership in this religious group require celibacy (full sexual abstinence):

– No

Does membership in this religious group require constraints on sexual activity (partial sexual abstinence):

– Field doesn't know

Does membership in this religious group require castration:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require fasting:

– Field doesn't know

Does membership in this religious group require forgone food opportunities (taboos on desired foods):

– Field doesn't know

Does membership in this religious group require permanent scarring or painful bodily alterations:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require painful physical positions or transitory painful wounds:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of adults:

"Adults" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition of a human who is 18-years-old or older and who is legally responsible for his/her actions, then please specify that difference in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of children:

"Children" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition, please specify that different in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Does membership in this religious group require self-sacrifice (suicide):

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of property/valuable items:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of time (e.g., attendance at meetings or services, regular prayer, etc.):

– Yes

Does membership in this religious group require physical risk taking:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require accepting ethical precepts:

– Yes

Does membership in this religious group require marginalization by out-group members:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require participation in small-scale rituals (private, household):

– Yes

Notes: It was very common for Tongshanshe members to meet and perform rituals at someone's home.

What is the average interval of time between performances (in hours):

Performances here refers to small-scale rituals.

– Field doesn't know

Does membership in this religious group require participation in large-scale rituals:

i.e. involving two or more households; includes large-scale “ceremonies” and “festivals.”

– Yes

On average, for large-scale rituals how many participants gather in one location:

– Field doesn't know

What is the average interval of time between performances (in hours):

Performances here refers to large-scale rituals.

– Field doesn't know

|

↳ Are there orthodoxy checks:

Orthodoxy checks are mechanisms used to ensure that rituals are interpreted in a standardized way, e.g. through the supervisory prominence of a professionalized priesthood or other system of governance, appeal to texts detailing the proper interpretation, etc.

– No

Notes: Tongshanshe accepted religious syncretism. In other words, there was no idea of orthodoxy or heterodoxy within Tongshanshe.

↳ Are there orthopraxy checks:

Orthopraxy checks are mechanisms used to ensure that rituals are performed in a standardized way, e.g. through the supervisory prominence of a professionalized priesthood or other system of governance, appeal to texts detailing the proper procedure, etc.

– No

↳ Does participation entail synchronic practices:

– No

↳ Is there use of intoxicants:

– No

Are extra-ritual in-group markers present:

E.g. special changes to appearance such as circumcision, tattoos, scarification, etc.

– Field doesn't know

Does the group employ fictive kinship terminology:

– No

Society and Institutions

Levels of Social Complexity

The society to which the religious group belongs is best characterized as (please choose one):

– Other [specify in comments]

Notes: Sectarianism. Unlike sectarian groups within Christianity, Tongshanshe was widely viewed as a sectarian group within the broad and general spectrum of Chinese popular religion. Most of its teachings were borrowed or modified from Confucianism, Buddhism, Daoism, and popular beliefs.

– A state

Notes: The broader political society of the period of my research is mainly Republican China (1927-1949) under the rule of the Nationalist Government. The conventional understanding of modern China

misinterprets the Nationalist Government as religion-friendly, in contrast to the atheist Communist Regime (1949 -). The Nationalist Government, however, also imposed strict control over all forms of religions and was very suppressive in many cases (See Rebecca Nedostup). Redemptive societies, such as the Tongshanshe, was the primary target of religious control in Republican China. Tongshanshe was banned in 1927. Compared to the Communist Regime whose societal control was very effective, the Nationalist Government's rural penetration was relatively weak. Many religious organizations, although officially banned by the government, continued their operation without much interference.

Welfare

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized famine relief:

– Yes

Notes: Many redemptive societies, including the Tongshanshe, are said to actively involved in famine relief. It didn't happen in my area of research.

Is famine relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized poverty relief:

– Yes

Notes: The history of Tongshanshe in Poyang began not only as a religious sect, as mentioned in the County Gazetteer, but also as a charity organization with a Traditional Chinese Medicine Clinic (zhongyiju, hereafter TCMC). The TCMC had its own name as the "Hall of Early Enlightenment" (Xianjueci). Around the years of 1932 and 1933, Tongshanshe established the TCMC. The TCMC offered free medicine to people, regardless of whether the requesters were members or not. The TCMC lasted for seven to eight years until around 1940. The financial shortfall was the primary factor that led to the disappearance of the TCMC. One leader of Tongshanshe points out that the TCMC was among the three most massive expenditures. One member who was a merchant and the owner of a restaurant, recalls that local merchants invited him to join the Tongshanshe in 1939, and he was asked for donations to support the TCMC and other charity activities. Offering money and medicine to the poor was considered great merit. It doesn't really matter how much one donates as long as one gives sincerely. People also recall that a few members from the Merchant Association were passionate about the charity functions of the Tongshanshe and offered money without hesitation. The establishment of the TCMC certainly reflects the real needs of people who were interested in the Tongshanshe. Although the merchant network within Tongshanshe might offer strong incentives for elite merchants who wanted to connect with other merchants and expand their interests, the direct motivation behind the merchants' joining the Tongshanshe was still predominantly related to health and healing.

Is poverty relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm:

– Field doesn't know

Is institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Education

Does the religious group provide formal education to its adherents:

– No

Is formal education available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group:

– No

Bureaucracy

Do the group's adherents interact with a formal bureaucracy within their group:

– Yes

Notes: See notes on leadership.

Do the group's adherents interact with other institutional bureaucracies:

– No

Notes: The situation may vary significantly in different regions. In the case of study of Poyang, many of Tongshanshe leaders were also the leaders of the local merchant association or even Nationalist Party members. I believe Tongshanshe was an important channel for merchants to expand their networks.

Public Works

Does the religious group in question provide public food storage:

– No

Is public food storage provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Does the religious group in question provide water management (irrigation, flood control):

– No

Is water management provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Does the religious group in question provide transportation infrastructure:

– No

Is transportation infrastructure provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Taxation

Does the religious group in question levy taxes or tithes:

– No

Are taxes levied on the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: Tongshanshe members were levied as regular Chinese citizens. Tongshanshe membership doesn't change their tax status.

Enforcement

Does the religious group in question provide an institutionalized police force:

– No

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized police force provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized judges:

– No

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized judicial system provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Does the religious group in question enforce institutionalized punishment:

– No

Are the group's adherents subject to institutionalized punishment enforced by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Does the religious group in question have a formal legal code:

– No

Are the group's adherents subject to a formal legal code provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Warfare

Does religious group in question possess an institutionalized military:

– Yes

Notes: In the early 1940s, Tongshanshe in Southern China absorbed a martial arts group known as the "Chai School Sect" (Chaimendao), also known as the "Big Sword Society" (Dadaohui) (note: there were many Big Sword Societies in rural China; most of them had no direct affiliations) into its organization. The Tongshanshe organization was divided into two separate sects known as the "Civil Branch (wenban)" and the "Martial Branch (wuban)." The absorption of martial arts groups also possibly went parallel with Tongshanshe highest leader Peng Ruzun's ambitious plan of turning himself into the emperor of China. Peng Ruzun dreamed himself to be the future emperor of China. Peng turned the history of Tongshanshe into three periods: Period one is called "Universal Deliverance (pudu)" when the TSS organization develops and absorbs people into the sect, preparing for the future. Period two is called "Close the Door (shouyuan)", when warriors and heroes join the Tongshanshe, and organize violent revolts against the secular regime. During this period, the Tongshanshe will defeat the secular power. Period three is known as the "Realization of the Way (liaodao)." During this period, the earthly power is already under the control of Tongshanshe. All the Tongshanshe members will enjoy great happiness and transform into immortals. Peng Ruzun claimed that his son Peng Baoshan would be the future emperor of China. Chinese scholar Qin Baoqi notes that Peng Ruzun already declared himself as the future emperor of China in 1929. Peng claimed that the end of the world was near, and the new emperor would be born in Sichuan soon. CCP's propaganda identifies the Chai School Sect as a key tool in Tongshanshe's plan of turning Peng Ruzun into the emperor. The Tongshanshe's militarization process might have also received patronage from Japan during the Second Sino-Japanese War. As early as 1933, Peng Ruzun sent his second son Peng Baoshan to Manchukuo and met Puyi secretly. Peng Baoshan promised Puyi that he would train a million "sacred soldiers (shenbing)" and return the throne of the Qing Empire to Puyi. Peng Baoshan's activity was discovered by the Nationalist Government. The government responded by labeling Peng Ruzun as a wanted criminal and further tightened its ban on Tongshanshe. From then on, Tongshanshe became more and more passionate about absorbing local militias, including the Big Sword Society, to defeat the Nationalist Government and fulfill Peng Ruzun's dream of becoming China's new emperor. During the 1940s, Tongshanshe with the assistance of its martial arts groups launched several violent revolts against the Nationalist Government. It also continued after the Communist Party's takeover and was finally suppressed by the CCP.

↳ Does the religious group in question have the power to conscript:

– No

↳ Does the religious group in question maintain a full-time military corps (e.g. Swiss Guard):

– No

↳ Does the religious group in question maintain a standing army:

– No

Do the group's adherents participate in an institutionalized military provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Are the group's adherents protected by or subject to an institutionalized military provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Written Language

Does the religious group in question possess its own distinct written language:

– No

Is a non-religion-specific written language available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Is a non-religion-specific written language used by the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Calendar

Does the religious group in question possess a formal calendar:

– Yes

Notes: Details unknown. It was only mentioned in the archives.

Is a formal calendar provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Field doesn't know

Food Production

Does the religious group in question provide food for themselves:

– No

Is food provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

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